

thiourea, triethanolamine, selenate, tellurates, alkali and alkaline earth metal ions and lanthanides do not interfere upto 2500 ppm. Interference due to Fe^{III} is eliminated by masking with trisodium phosphate (2 g). The tolerance limits for other ions (ppm, in parenthesis) are as follows: Cu^{II} (200); Mo^{VI} (1200); Zr^{IV} (120); W^{VI} (100); Ti^{IV} (250); Nb^{V} , Ta^{V} (250); Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Al^{III} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} (2200); phosphate, borate, phthalate (2500); oxalate, tartrate, citrate, arsenate (1500); chlorate, bromate, iodate, thiosulphate (1200).

Application of the method: The validity of the method was tested in two vanadium-tungsten steels and a tungsten-free low alloy steel. The results are shown in Table 1. The sample containing about 3 mg of vanadium was dissolved in 40% HNO_3 . Tungsten was removed before the determination of vanadium as hydrated oxide by filtration. The vanadium content of the filtrate was then determined as described above. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN STEEL SAMPLES

Sample	Certified V%	Found* V%	Standard deviation
Alloy steel (64a)	1.57	1.562	± 0.0084
High speed steel (241/1)	1.57	1.556	± 0.0078
Low alloy steel (25 2)	0.46	0.452	± 0.0092

* Average of six determinations.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium using *o*-Dianisidine as Reagent

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THE literature reports the formation of vanadium complexes with many organic reagents¹ and their extraction from aqueous solution into various organic solvents for analytical purposes². In this

paper a method is described for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium in alloy steels especially high speed steels by reaction with *o*-dianisidine. It has been observed that vanadium(V) reacts with *o*-dianisidine in acid medium forming a yellow-orange colour having λ_{max} at 440 nm, molar absorptivity $3.01 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandel sensitivity $0.00156 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.05–2 ppm of vanadium(V). The influence of various experimental factors such as reaction period, temperature, concentration of reagent and the influence of diverse ions has been studied. The method is simple and rapid. Instead of deleterious separation of Cr (which interferes) by extraction, the interference is avoided by dual wavelength measurement of absorbance and reference to a correction graph.

Experimental

A 0.05% solution of *o*-dianisidine in dilute sulphuric acid was made. Standard vanadium(V) solution was made by dissolving vanadium pentoxide (A.R., 1.786 g; equivalent to 1.0 g of V) in a minimum volume of 10% NaOH solution, neutralising the surplus alkali with HCl and diluting to 1 dm³ with distilled water to give the stock solution. A 100 ml portion of the solution was further diluted to 1 dm³ to give working solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of V^V.

Standard chromium(VI) solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ of Cr was prepared from potassium dichromate (A.R.). Standard iron(II) solution was prepared by dissolving pure iron powder (1.0 g) in minimum quantity of HCl and diluting to 1 dm³ and was used for the background correction.

Acid mixture contained perchloric acid (sp. gr. 1.67; 1100 ml), phosphoric acid (sp. gr. 1.75; 300 ml) and water (100 ml).

Preparation of calibration graph: Aliquots of standard vanadium solution containing 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 μg of vanadium(V) were mixed separately with iron(II) solution (10 ml) and acid mixture (15 ml) and fumed on a hot-plate until the volume was reduced to 5 ml. The solutions were then cooled, diluted to 25 ml, mixed with *o*-dianisidine reagent (4 ml), allowed to stand for 5 min at room temperature and diluted to 100 ml in a measuring flask. The absorbance of the yellow-orange solution was measured at 440 nm within 30 min. A plot of absorbance vs amount of V^V was linear.

Correction graph for chromium: The iron(II) solution (10 ml of 10 mg ml⁻¹) was mixed with each of the 0, 10, 30, 50 and 100 μg of chromium(VI) solution. The solutions were then fumed with the acid mixture (15 ml), then cooled and diluted to 25 ml and treated for colour development (as given in the procedure for vanadium) and the absorbance measured at 400 nm and 440 nm. A plot of absorbances at 400 nm against that at 440 nm was linear (Fig. 1). In unknown samples, a reference of

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absorbance at 400 nm to the correction graph produces Cr contribution at 440 nm which should be subtracted.

Fig. 1. Chromium correction graph.

Determination in steel samples: The sample (~0.25 g) was opened by treating with the acid mixture (15 ml) and analysed as in the preparation of calibration graph. Experiments were repeated with different samples of British Chemical Standard steels.

The waste solutions containing *o*-dianisidine reagent should be carefully disposed or the reagent destroyed either by alkaline permanganate oxidation or by evaporation and incineration.

Results and Discussion

A replicate of six analyses on different amount of samples produced the amount of vanadium that agreed well with the claimed level in the British Chemical Standard steels (Table I). The interference of Cr, Ni, Co, Mo, Mn, Cu, Al, W, Ti, Fe, Nb and Ta were tested, and only Cr^{VI} interfered by forming a similar yellow-orange complex. The composition of the complex was studied at pH 1 by mole-ratio method and found to have a 1 : 4 metal-composition.

TABLE I—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(V) WITH *o*-DIANISIDINE

Sl. no.	Sample	V Certified %	V Found (n=6) %	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation %
1.	BCS 251/1	0.65	0.654	0.011 8	1.80
2.	BCS 252/1	0.51	0.480	0.100	2.08
3.	BCS 253/1	0.38	0.342	0.014	5.78
4.	BCS 254/1	0.15	0.160	0.011	6.88
5.	BCS 172/2	0.04	0.042	0.002 4	5.71

The method has the advantage that it can be applied to all kinds of alloy steels containing

chromium and vanadium(v) concentration as low as 0.15–0.65%. The recovery was within tolerable limits of accuracy and precision. The proposed method of correcting the Cr interference is simple and rapid.

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A Spectrophotometric Assay Procedure for Estimation of Fructose in Presence of Glucose

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THE estimation of fructose makes use of its reducing characteristics on its dehydration to hydroxy-methyl furfural and then carrying out a reaction with a suitable colouring agent. However, both these characteristics are also shown by glucose. Due to similar reactions of the two sugars, estimation of one in presence of the other has been proved to be a problem. Resorcinol–thiourea–hydrochloric acid¹, anthrone–sulphuric acid², cystein–hydrochloric acid–sulphuric acid³ and phenol–sulphuric acid⁴ reagents have been used to estimate fructose in presence of glucose. In the present study, we have adopted a more sensitive and equally accurate procedure for estimating fructose in presence of glucose. Two complexing agents, namely, 0.5% pyrogallol/0.5% resorcinol were tested in varying concentrations of either hydrochloric acid or phosphoric acid. These reagents made colour complexes with fructose, whereas glucose did not produce colour under similar experimental conditions.

Standard sugar solution (2 ml) was mixed with either of the complexing agents (2 ml) and the mixture heated for 2 min in a boiling water-bath and then cooled under tap-water. The appearance of